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(57) Abstract :
 The present invention relates to an advanced insect repellent device that utilizes a combination of ultrasonic sound waves, LED light emissions, and natural plant-based insect-repelling compounds to provide a comprehensive and effective solution for repelling insects, particularly mosquitoes. The device is designed to be portable, energy-efficient, and environmentally friendly, offering long-lasting protection without the use of toxic chemicals. It includes a control system that allows the user to adjust the intensity of the ultrasonic waves, LED lights, and the release rate of the insect-repelling compounds. The device features a rechargeable power source, a diffusion system for evenly dispersing the repellent, and wireless connectivity for remote operation via a mobile application. Additionally, the device incorporates smart functionalities such as motion detection, environmental sensing, and power management to optimize performance and extend battery life.

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